

Online Companion: Embedding Dependencies Within Distributionally Robust Optimization of Modern Power Systems

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This manuscript serves as an electronic companion to [1]. Section 1 defines the Wasserstein probability metric. Sections 2 and 3 provide the final optimization model under the metric-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_1$ and the copula-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_2$, respectively. The real-time operational problem for the out-of-sample simulation is given in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 gives the economic and technical input data of our case study built upon the IEEE reliability test system.

1 Wasserstein probability metric

The distance between two distributions, namely $\mathbb{Q}_1$ and $\mathbb{Q}_2$, is assessed via the Wasserstein metric, whose mathematical formulation is given in Definition 1.1. This metric can be seen as an optimal transportation problem that aims to minimize the cost of transporting the probability mass from $\mathbb{Q}_1$ to $\mathbb{Q}_2$.

Definition 1.1 (*Wasserstein metric [2]*) *The Wasserstein metric $d : \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is defined as*

$$d(\mathbb{Q}_1, \mathbb{Q}_2) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{\Pi \in \Xi^2} \int \|\tilde{\xi}_1 - \tilde{\xi}_2\| \Pi(d\tilde{\xi}_1, d\tilde{\xi}_2) \\ \text{s.t. } \Pi \text{ is a joint distribution of } \tilde{\xi}_1 \text{ and } \tilde{\xi}_2 \\ \text{with marginals } \mathbb{Q}_1 \text{ and } \mathbb{Q}_2, \text{ respectively} \end{array} \right\}. \quad (1)$$

The objective function in (1) represents the transportation cost of moving the probability mass from $\mathbb{Q}_1$ to $\mathbb{Q}_2$. The chosen cost for moving each data sample is the norm $\|\tilde{\xi}_1 - \tilde{\xi}_2\|$, defined as the Wasserstein distance. The joint distribution Π , which is the optimization variable, refers to the optimal transportation plan. Based on this definition, the Wasserstein metric-based ambiguity set collects the closest distributions from an empirical one $\hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{\tilde{\xi}_i}$, that is typically constituted of N observed samples, each assigned with probability $\frac{1}{N}$. We thereby mathematically define the Wasserstein ambiguity set as follows:

$$\mathcal{M}_1 = \left\{ \mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{F} \mid d(\mathbb{Q}, \hat{\mathbb{Q}}_N) \leq \theta_1 \right\}. \quad (2)$$

2 Model reformulation under metric-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_1$

$$\min_{\substack{g, \bar{r}, \underline{r}, V, \lambda, \sigma_i, \gamma_i, \\ \tau_f, \lambda_f, \sigma_{f,i}, \gamma_{f,i,1}, \gamma_{f,i,2}, \\ \bar{\tau}_g, \bar{\lambda}_g, \bar{\sigma}_{g,i}, \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1}, \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2}, \underline{\tau}_g, \underline{\lambda}_g, \underline{\sigma}_{g,i}, \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1}, \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2}}} c^\top g + \bar{c}^\top \bar{r} + \underline{c}^\top \underline{r} + \lambda \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i \quad (3a)$$

s.t.

$$g + \bar{r} \leq p^{\max} \quad (3b)$$

$$g - \underline{r} \geq 0 \quad (3c)$$

$$0 \leq \underline{r} \leq r^{\max}; 0 \leq \bar{r} \leq r^{\max} \quad (3d)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top g + \mathbf{1}^\top W \mu - \mathbf{1}^\top d = 0 \quad (3e)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top V + \mathbf{1}^\top W = 0 \quad (3f)$$

$$\begin{cases} c^\top V \hat{\xi}_i + \gamma_i^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \sigma_i & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \gamma_i - c^\top V\|_* \leq \lambda & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \gamma_i \geq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{cases} \quad (3g)$$

$$\left. \begin{cases} \bar{\tau}_g + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\bar{\lambda}_g \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{\sigma}_{g,i} \right) \leq 0 \\ V_g \hat{\xi}_i - \bar{r}_g - \bar{\tau}_g + \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1} - V_g\|_* \leq \bar{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2}\|_* \leq \bar{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,1} \geq 0; \bar{\gamma}_{g,i,2} \geq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{cases} \right\} \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3h)$$

$$\left. \begin{cases} \underline{\tau}_g + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\underline{\lambda}_g \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \underline{\sigma}_{g,i} \right) \leq 0 \\ -V_g \hat{\xi}_i - \underline{r}_g - \underline{\tau}_g + \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \underline{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \underline{\sigma}_{g,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1} + V_g\|_* \leq \underline{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2}\|_* \leq \underline{\lambda}_g & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,1} \geq 0; \underline{\gamma}_{g,i,2} \geq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{cases} \right\} \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3i)$$

$$\left. \begin{cases} \tau_f + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\lambda_f \rho + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{f,i} \right) \leq 0 \\ \left(T_f^P (g + V \hat{\xi}) + T_f^W W (\mu + \hat{\xi}) - T_f^D (d) - f_f^{\max} \right) - \tau_f + \gamma_{f,i,1}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \sigma_{f,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \gamma_{f,i,2}^\top (h - Q \hat{\xi}_i) \leq \sigma_{f,i} & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \gamma_{f,i,1} - (T_f^G V + T_f^W W)\|_* \leq \lambda_f & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \|Q^\top \gamma_{f,i,2}\|_* \leq \lambda_f & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \gamma_i \geq 0 & \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \end{cases} \right\} \forall f \in \mathcal{F}. \quad (3j)$$

3 Model reformulation under copula-based ambiguity set $\mathcal{M}_2$

$$c^\top g + \bar{c}^\top \bar{r} + \underline{c}^\top \underline{r} + \alpha \theta_1 \quad (4a)$$

$$+ \beta \theta_2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{g, \bar{r}, \underline{r}, V, \alpha, \beta, \sigma_i, \zeta_{ki}^{(1)}, \zeta_{ki}^{(2)}, \mu_{wi}^{(0)}, \mu_{kij}^{(1)}, \mu_{kij}^{(2)}, \mu_{kij}^{(3)}, \mu_{kij}^{(4)}, \mu_{kij}^{(5)}, \mu_{kij}^{(6)}, \mu_{kij}^{(7)}, \mu_{kij}^{(8)}, \mu_{kij}^{(9)}, \mu_{kij}^{(10)}, \mu_{kij}^{(11)}, \\ & \bar{\alpha}_g, \bar{\beta}_g, \bar{\sigma}_g, \bar{\sigma}_{gi}, \bar{\zeta}_{gki}^{(1)}, \bar{\zeta}_{gki}^{(2)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(0)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(1)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(2)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(3)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(4)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(5)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(6)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(7)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(8)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(9)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(10)}, \bar{\mu}_{gkij}^{(11)}, \\ & \underline{\alpha}_g, \underline{\beta}_g, \underline{\sigma}_g, \underline{\sigma}_{gi}, \underline{\zeta}_{gki}^{(1)}, \underline{\zeta}_{gki}^{(2)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(0)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(1)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(2)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(3)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(4)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(5)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(6)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(7)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(8)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(9)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(10)}, \underline{\mu}_{gkij}^{(11)}, \\ & \alpha_f, \beta_f, \tau_f, \sigma_{fi}, \zeta_{fki}^{(1)}, \zeta_{fki}^{(2)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(0)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(1)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(2)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(3)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(4)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(5)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(6)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(7)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(8)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(9)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(10)}, \mu_{fkij}^{(11)}, \lambda_{fkij} \end{aligned}$$

$$s.t. \quad g + \bar{r} \leq p^{\max} \quad (4b)$$

$$g - r \geq 0 \quad (4c)$$

$$0 \leq r \leq r^{\max}; 0 \leq \bar{r} \leq r^{\max} \quad (4d)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top g + \mathbf{1}^\top W \mu - \mathbf{1}^\top d = 0 \quad (4e)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top V + \mathbf{1}^\top W = 0 \quad (4f)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & -\zeta_i^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \zeta_i^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \mu^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{W}|} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{kji}^{(3)} \bar{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{kji}^{(4)} \bar{\xi}_k^{\min} + \mu_{kji}^{(6)} + \frac{1}{N} \mu_{kji}^{(7)} + \mu_{kji}^{(9)} \bar{V} \xi_k^{\max} - \mu_{kji}^{(10)} \bar{V} \xi_k^{\min} \right) \leq \sigma_i \quad \forall i \\ & V_k^\top c + \zeta_{ki}^{(1)} - Q_k^\top \mu_i^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{kji}^{(3)} + \mu_{kji}^{(4)} + \bar{V} \mu_{kji}^{(10)} - \bar{V} \mu_{kji}^{(9)} \right) = 0 \quad \forall k, i \\ & \frac{1}{N} \zeta_{ik}^{(2)} - \mu_{kji}^{(1)} \hat{\xi}_{kj} - \mu_{kji}^{(2)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\min} - \mu_{kji}^{(3)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\max} + \mu_{kji}^{(4)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\min} + \mu_{kji}^{(5)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\max} - \mu_{kji}^{(6)} + \frac{1}{N} \lambda_k \leq 0 \quad \forall k, j, i \\ & \mu_{kji}^{(1)} + \mu_{kji}^{(2)} + \mu_{kji}^{(3)} - \mu_{kji}^{(4)} - \mu_{kji}^{(5)} = 0 \quad \forall k, j, i \\ & -\mu_{kji}^{(7)} + \mu_{kji}^{(8)} + \mu_{kji}^{(9)} - \mu_{kji}^{(10)} - \mu_{kji}^{(11)} = 0 \quad \forall k, j, i \\ & \mu_{kji}^{(7)} - \lambda_k = 0 \quad \forall k, j, i \\ & \mu_{kji}^{(7)} - \mu_{kji}^{(8)} \xi_k^{\min} - \mu_{kji}^{(9)} \xi_k^{\max} + \mu_{kji}^{(10)} \xi_k^{\min} + \mu_{kji}^{(11)} \xi_k^{\max} \leq 0 \quad \forall k, j, i \\ & \|\zeta_i^{(1)}\|_* \leq \alpha \quad \forall i \\ & \|\zeta_i^{(2)}\|_* \leq \beta \quad \forall i. \end{aligned} \right. \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (4g)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \bar{\tau}_g + \frac{1}{\bar{c}} \left(\bar{\alpha}_g \theta_1 + \bar{\beta}_g \theta_2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{\sigma}_{gi} \right) \leq 0 \\ & -\bar{\tau}_g - \bar{\sigma}_g - \bar{\zeta}_{1gi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \bar{\zeta}_{1gi}^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \bar{\mu}_{1gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{W}|} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\bar{\mu}_{1kgi}^{(3)} \bar{\xi}_k^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{1kgi}^{(4)} \bar{\xi}_k^{\min} + \bar{\mu}_{1kgi}^{(6)} + \frac{1}{N} \bar{\mu}_{1kgi}^{(7)} + \bar{\mu}_{1kgi}^{(9)} \bar{V} \xi_k^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{1kgi}^{(10)} \bar{V} \xi_k^{\min} \right) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{gi} \quad \forall i \\ & -\bar{\zeta}_{2gi}^{(1)\top} \hat{\xi}_i - \bar{\zeta}_{2gi}^{(2)\top} \hat{F}_i + \bar{\mu}_{2gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{W}|} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\bar{\mu}_{2kgi}^{(3)} \bar{\xi}_k^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{2kgi}^{(4)} \bar{\xi}_k^{\min} + \bar{\mu}_{2kgi}^{(6)} + \frac{1}{N} \bar{\mu}_{2kgi}^{(7)} + \bar{\mu}_{2kgi}^{(9)} \bar{V} \xi_k^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{2kgi}^{(10)} \bar{V} \xi_k^{\min} \right) \leq \bar{\sigma}_{gi} \quad \forall i \\ & V_{gk} + \bar{\zeta}_{1gi}^{(1)} - Q_k^\top \bar{\mu}_{1gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\bar{\mu}_{1gkij}^{(4)} + \bar{\mu}_{1gkij}^{(3)} + \bar{V} \bar{\mu}_{1gkij}^{(10)} - \bar{V} \bar{\mu}_{1gkij}^{(9)} \right) = 0 \quad \forall k, i \\ & \bar{\zeta}_{2gi}^{(1)} - Q_k^\top \bar{\mu}_{2gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\bar{\mu}_{2gkij}^{(4)} + \bar{\mu}_{2gkij}^{(3)} + \bar{V} \bar{\mu}_{2gkij}^{(10)} - \bar{V} \bar{\mu}_{2gkij}^{(9)} \right) = 0 \quad \forall k, i \\ & \frac{1}{N} \bar{\zeta}_{vgki}^{(2)} - \bar{\mu}_{vkij}^{(1)} \hat{\xi}_{kj} - \bar{\mu}_{vkij}^{(2)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\min} - \bar{\mu}_{vkij}^{(3)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\max} + \bar{\mu}_{vkij}^{(4)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\min} + \bar{\mu}_{vkij}^{(5)} \bar{\xi}_{kj}^{\max} - \bar{\mu}_{vkij}^{(6)} + \frac{1}{N} \bar{\lambda}_{vgki} \leq 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\ & \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(1)} + \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(2)} + \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(3)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(4)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(5)} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\ & -\bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(7)} + \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(8)} + \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(9)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(10)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(11)} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\ & \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(7)} - \bar{\lambda}_{vgki} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\ & \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(7)} - \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(8)} \xi_k^{\min} - \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(9)} \xi_k^{\max} + \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(10)} \xi_k^{\min} + \bar{\mu}_{vgkij}^{(11)} \xi_k^{\max} \leq 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\ & \|\bar{\zeta}_{vgi}^{(1)}\|_* \leq \bar{\alpha}_g \quad \forall v, i \\ & \|\bar{\zeta}_{vgi}^{(2)}\|_* \leq \bar{\beta}_g \quad \forall v, i \end{aligned} \right. \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (4h)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
& \tau_g + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\alpha_g \theta_1 + \beta_g \theta_2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{gi} \right) \leq 0 \\
& -\tau_g - \tau_g - \zeta_{1gi}^{(1)\top} \widehat{\xi}_i - \zeta_{1gi}^{(2)\top} \widehat{F}_i + \mu_{1gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{W}|} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{1kgi}^{(3)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{1kgi}^{(4)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} + \mu_{1kgi}^{(6)\top} + \frac{1}{N} \mu_{1kgi}^{(7)\top} + \mu_{1kgi}^{(9)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{1kgi}^{(10)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} \right) \leq \sigma_{gi} \quad \forall i \\
& -\zeta_{2gi}^{(1)\top} \widehat{\xi}_i - \zeta_{2gi}^{(2)\top} \widehat{F}_i + \mu_{2gi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{W}|} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{2kgi}^{(3)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{2kgi}^{(4)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} + \mu_{2kgi}^{(6)\top} + \frac{1}{N} \mu_{2kgi}^{(7)\top} + \mu_{2kgi}^{(9)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{2kgi}^{(10)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} \right) \leq \sigma_{gi} \quad \forall i \\
& -V_{gk} + \zeta_{1gki}^{(1)} - Q_k^\top \mu_{1gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{1gkij}^{(4)} + \mu_{1gkij}^{(3)} + \overline{V} \mu_{1gkij}^{(10)} - \overline{V} \mu_{1gkij}^{(9)} \right) = 0 \quad \forall k, i \\
& \zeta_{2gki}^{(1)} - Q_k^\top \mu_{2gi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{2gkij}^{(4)} + \mu_{2gkij}^{(3)} + \overline{V} \mu_{2gkij}^{(10)} - \overline{V} \mu_{2gkij}^{(9)} \right) = 0 \quad \forall k, i \\
& \frac{1}{N} \zeta_{v g k i}^{(2)} - \mu_{v k j i}^{(1)} \widehat{\xi}_{k j} - \mu_{v k j i}^{(2)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} - \mu_{v k j i}^{(3)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} + \mu_{v k j i}^{(4)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} + \mu_{v k j i}^{(5)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{v k j i}^{(6)} + \frac{1}{N} \lambda_{v g k i} \leq 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \mu_{v g k i j}^{(1)} + \mu_{v g k i j}^{(2)} + \mu_{v g k i j}^{(3)} - \mu_{v g k i j}^{(4)} - \mu_{v g k i j}^{(5)} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& -\mu_{v g k j i}^{(7)} + \mu_{v g k j i}^{(8)} + \mu_{v g k j i}^{(9)} - \mu_{v g k j i}^{(10)} - \mu_{v g k j i}^{(11)} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \mu_{v g k j i}^{(7)} - \lambda_{v g k i} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \mu_{v g k j i}^{(7)} - \mu_{v g k j i}^{(8)} \xi_k^{\min} - \mu_{v g k j i}^{(9)} \xi_k^{\max} + \mu_{v g k j i}^{(10)} \xi_k^{\min} + \mu_{v g k j i}^{(11)} \xi_k^{\max} \leq 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \|\zeta_{v g i}^{(1)}\|_* \leq \alpha_g \quad \forall v, i \\
& \|\zeta_{v g i}^{(2)}\|_* \leq \beta_g \quad \forall v, i
\end{aligned} \right\} \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \tag{4i}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
& \tau_f + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\alpha_f \theta_1 + \beta_f \theta_2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{fi} \right) \leq 0 \\
& -f_f^{\max} + T_f^{\mathcal{P}} g + T_f^{\mathcal{W}} W \mu - T_f^{\mathcal{D}} d - \tau_f - \zeta_{1fi}^{(1)\top} \widehat{\xi}_i - \zeta_{1fi}^{(2)\top} \widehat{F}_i + \mu_{1fi}^{(0)\top} h \\
& \quad + \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{W}|} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{1kfi}^{(3)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{1kfi}^{(4)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} + \mu_{1kfi}^{(6)\top} + \frac{1}{N} \mu_{1kfi}^{(7)\top} + \mu_{1kfi}^{(9)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{1kfi}^{(10)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} \right) \leq \sigma_{fi} \quad \forall i \\
& -\zeta_{2fi}^{(1)\top} \widehat{\xi}_i - \zeta_{2fi}^{(2)\top} \widehat{F}_i + \mu_{2fi}^{(0)\top} h + \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{W}|} \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{2kfi}^{(3)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{2kfi}^{(4)\top} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} + \mu_{2kfi}^{(6)\top} + \frac{1}{N} \mu_{2kfi}^{(7)\top} + \mu_{2kfi}^{(9)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{2kfi}^{(10)\top} \overline{V} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} \right) \leq \sigma_{fi} \quad \forall i \\
& T_f^{\mathcal{P}} V + T_f^{\mathcal{W}} W + \zeta_{1fki}^{(1)} - Q_k^\top \mu_{1fi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{1fkij}^{(4)} + \mu_{1fkij}^{(3)} + \overline{V} \mu_{1fkij}^{(10)} - \overline{V} \mu_{1fkij}^{(9)} \right) = 0 \quad \forall k, i \\
& \zeta_{2fki}^{(1)} - Q_k^\top \mu_{2fi}^{(0)} + \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mu_{2fkij}^{(4)} + \mu_{2fkij}^{(3)} + \overline{V} \mu_{2fkij}^{(10)} - \overline{V} \mu_{2fkij}^{(9)} \right) = 0 \quad \forall k, i \\
& \frac{1}{N} f_{v f k i}^{(2)} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(1)} \widehat{\xi}_{k j} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(2)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(3)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} + \mu_{v f k j i}^{(4)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\min} + \mu_{v f k j i}^{(5)} \widehat{\xi}_k^{\max} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(6)} + \frac{1}{N} \lambda_{v f k i} \leq 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \mu_{v f k i j}^{(1)} + \mu_{v f k i j}^{(2)} + \mu_{v f k i j}^{(3)} - \mu_{v f k i j}^{(4)} - \mu_{v f k i j}^{(5)} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& -\mu_{v f k j i}^{(7)} + \mu_{v f k j i}^{(8)} + \mu_{v f k j i}^{(9)} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(10)} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(11)} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \mu_{v f k j i}^{(7)} - \lambda_{v f k i} = 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \mu_{v f k j i}^{(7)} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(8)} \xi_k^{\min} - \mu_{v f k j i}^{(9)} \xi_k^{\max} + \mu_{v f k j i}^{(10)} \xi_k^{\min} + \mu_{v f k j i}^{(11)} \xi_k^{\max} \leq 0 \quad \forall v, k, j, i \\
& \|\zeta_{v f i}^{(1)}\|_* \leq \alpha_f \quad \forall v, i \\
& \|\zeta_{v f i}^{(2)}\|_* \leq \beta_f \quad \forall v, i
\end{aligned} \right\} \forall f \in \mathcal{F}$$

4 The real-time operational problem

This section presents the real-time operational optimization problem for the out-of-sample analysis. Given the realized uncertainty $\widehat{\xi}_j$ that refers to the wind power forecast error with respect to the day-ahead forecast μ , this problem writes as

$$\min_{V, \Delta d, \Delta w} c^\top V \widehat{\xi}_j + v_{\text{Shed}}^\top \Delta d \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } 0 \leq \Delta d \leq d \quad (5b)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta w \leq W(\mu + \widehat{\xi}_j) \quad (5c)$$

$$-\underline{r} \leq V \widehat{\xi}_j \leq \bar{r} \quad (5d)$$

$$\mathbf{1}^\top V \widehat{\xi}_j + \mathbf{1}^\top W \widehat{\xi}_j + \mathbf{1}^\top \Delta d - \mathbf{1}^\top \Delta w = 0. \quad (5e)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_f^{\mathcal{P}} (g + V \widehat{\xi}) + \mathbf{T}_f^{\mathcal{W}} W (\mu + \widehat{\xi}) - \mathbf{T}_f^{\mathcal{D}} (d - \Delta d) \leq f_f^{\max} \quad \forall f \in \mathfrak{F}, \quad (5f)$$

The objective function (5a) models the total recourse operational cost, incurred by the recourse production cost of conventional generating units (the first term) and the load shedding cost (the second term). The parameter $v_{\text{Shed}} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{D}|}$ refers to the value of lost load. The wind spillage cost is assumed to be zero. Constraints (5b) and (5c) limit the wind power spillage $\Delta w \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{W}|}$ and the load shedding $\Delta d \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{D}|}$. The recourse production $V \widehat{\xi}_j$ of conventional generating units is limited in (5d) by the reserve capacities $\underline{r}$ and $\bar{r}$ procured in the day-ahead stage. The real-time power balance is ensured by (5e). Finally, the maximum capacity limits are ensured by (5f) for each transmission line $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.

5 Input data

We build our case study upon the IEEE reliability test system [3]. All economic data are available in [4]. The input data are given by Table 1. It includes technical data of conventional generating units, including their production cost c_p in \$/MWh, upward reserve capacity procurement cost $\bar{c}_p$ in \$/MW, downward reserve capacity procurement cost $\underline{c}_p$ in \$/MW, capacity $g_p^{\max}$ in MW, maximum upward regulation capability $\bar{r}_p^{\max}$ in MW, and maximum downward regulation capability $\underline{r}_p^{\max}$ in MW. In addition, Table 1 includes the day-ahead wind power forecast μ in MW and their installed capacity $W_{(w,w)}$ in MW. This table also gives the input data of 17 loads, including their consumption d in MW and the value of lost load v_{Shed} in \$/MWh. Finally, the generating units, the wind farms, and the loads are connected via a 24-node network and their respective connecting node number are referred in the Table 1. The lines are characterized by their connecting nodes, their per-unit inverse susceptance $1/B$ as well as their maximum line capacity $f_f^{\max}$ in MW.

Table 1: Input Data

Generating units		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12					
Node		1	2	7	13	15	15	16	18	21	22	23	23					
c_p [\$/MWh]		13.32	13.32	20.7	20.93	26.11	10.52	10.52	6.02	5.47	7	10.52	10.89					
$\bar{c}_p$ [\$/MW]		1.68	1.68	3.30	4.07	1.89	5.48	5.48	4.98	5.53	8.00	3.45	5.11					
$\underline{c}_p$ [\$/MW]		2.32	2.32	4.67	3.93	3.11	3.52	3.52	5.02	4.97	6.00	2.52	2.89					
$P_p^{\max}$ [MW]		106.4	106.4	245	413.7	42	108.5	108.5	280	280	210	217	245					
$\bar{P}_p$ [MW]		48	48	84	216	42	36	36	60	60	48	48	48					
L_p [MW]		48	48	84	216	42	36	36	60	60	48	48	48					
Wind farms										1	2	3	4					
Node										3	5	16	21					
$P_q^{\max}$ [MW]												500	500					
Day-ahead wind power forecast [MW]												120.54	115.52					
Loads		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
Node		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
d [MW]		84	75	139	58	55	106	97	132	135	150	205	150	245	77	258	141	100
Y_{shed} [\$/MWh]		500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500
Lines: From node		1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	10	10
To node		2	3	5	4	6	9	24	9	10	10	8	9	10	11	12	11	12
$1/B$ [pu]		0.0146	0.2253	0.0907	0.1356	0.205	0.1271	0.084	0.111	0.094	0.0642	0.0652	0.1762	0.1762	0.084	0.084	0.084	0.084
$f_j^{\max}$ [MW]		175	175	350	175	175	400	175	350	175	350	175	175	400	400	400	400	400
Lines: From node		11	11	12	12	13	14	15	15	16	16	17	17	18	19	20	21	21
To node		13	14	13	23	23	16	16	21	24	17	19	18	22	21	20	23	22
$1/B$ [pu]		0.0488	0.0426	0.0488	0.0985	0.0884	0.0594	0.0172	0.0249	0.0529	0.0263	0.0234	0.0143	0.1069	0.0132	0.0203	0.0112	0.0692
$f_j^{\max}$ [MW]		500	500	500	500	250	250	500	400	500	500	500	500	500	1000	1000	1000	500

References

- [1] A. Arrigo, J. Kazempour, Z. De Grève, J.-F. Toubéau and F. Vallée, “Embedding Dependencies Within Distributionally Robust Optimization of Modern Power Systems,” submitted to the *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 2021.
- [2] L. V. Kantorovich and G. S. Rubinshtein, On a space of totally additive functions, *Vestnik Leningradskogo Universiteta*, 13 (1958), pp. 52-59.
- [3] C. Grigg *et al.*, “The IEEE reliability test system 1996. A report prepared by the reliability test system task force of the application of probability methods subcommittee”, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 14(3), pp. 1010-1020, 1999.
- [4] C. Ordoudis, P. Pinson, J. M. Morales and M. Zugno, “An updated version of the IEEE RTS 24-bus system for electricity market and power system operation studies”, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), 2016. <http://orbit.dtu.dk/files/120568114/An>